

THE PROBLEM IN TRANSLATION OF PROVERBS FROM
ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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Annotation: *Paremiological units especially, proverbs and sayings are inseparable part of a particular nation, and they are connected with their culture, life and history. Therefore, some scholars and translators find difficulties in finding exact alternative of some lexical items while translating such phraseological units. This paper focuses on investigating the translation problems of proverbs from English into Uzbek. There are some examples of proverbs that cannot be translated directly from English into Uzbek.*

Key words: *proverbs, paremiological units, phraseological units, translation, meaning, change, equivalent, problem, method, semantics, analysis*

Proverbs are the result of people's experience that reflects people's history, traditions and culture. According to the definition of Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs, Proverbs are main and concrete paremiological units, mostly known and repeated, which express a truth, based on common sense or the practical experience of humanity. They are traditional sayings which offer advice or present a moral in a short and pithy manner. Proverbs can also be used to make a

conversation more meaningful. All over world, when people use proverbs in their speeches , it is the sign of being a good orator.

“Idiomatic expressions are untranslatable” and “words cannot be added and omitted” V. G. Belinskiy (as cited G. Salomov,1961). Here, we come across with the problem concerning in the title. V. G. Belinskiy argued that proverbs had to be translated how it had been in original version without addition or omission of the word. On the other hand, translating proverbs directly from one language into another in literary works may have a bad impact on the style of the proverbs. Later, Ghaybulla Salomov filled his view and admitted that translating may not be simple task, but it must be creative work. Exactness and creativeness in translation should be filled each other. However, we should remember that in some cases, one of them (exactness or creativeness) may be essential than the other one. Translate proverbs and idioms without a context is extremely hard task, since their translations are distinguished in various occasions.

Politeness costs little, but yields much (English)

Yaxshi gap bilan ilon inidan chiqar; (Uzbek)

Sovuq-sovuq so`zlasang, qilich chiqar qinidan , iliq-iliq so`zlasang, ilon chiqar qinidan. (Uzbek)

This proverb tries to tell us about the value of politeness and it can make us be polite and kind. Here, we may understand that it does not take much for someone to be polite, but it will be beneficial for that person at the end. If we translate the proverb "Politeness costs little, but yields much" word-for-word as xushmuomalalik arzon, lekin ancha hosil beradi. We considered some information is missing in translation, for this reason in our translation, we added some Uzbek phrases.

Money after bad, throw good. (English).

Puli kuygan qalampir chaynar. (Uzbek).

In this proverb, words "bad"- "yomon", "good"- "yaxshi" are used in connection of the money. Not surprisingly, the words "bad" and "good" are being

emphasized how the money is earned not its bad and good conservation. There is no doubt that not all money is found in an honest way, because, today more and more people sacrifice many things for money. It is possible to use the word "bad" in relation to money received through the sacrifice of someone. However, there is no similarity between the English version and the Uzbek version of this proverb. The Uzbek equivalent is very different from the English version. None of the words, such as "Kuymoq", "Qalampir chaynamoq" exist in the English version.

In conclusion, it is obvious that there are a great number of proverbs in both English and Uzbek languages. While translating English proverbs into Uzbek language, translation problems may occur. Translation problems might be different in various examples. Learning proverbs may improve learners' language skills and help to get to know large amount of knowledge about other nation's cultures. This is because, proverbs of each nation are the representation of their life. Unless, many of the proverbs are translated into another language by taking account their literal and cultural peculiarities, their meanings will not be obvious.

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